

Relativistic quantum reference frames: the operational meaning of spin

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The spin is the prime example of a qubit. Encoding and decoding information in the spin qubit is operationally well defined through the Stern-Gerlach set-up in the non-relativistic (i.e., low velocity) limit. However, an operational definition of the spin in the relativistic regime is missing. The origin of this difficulty lies in the fact that, on the one hand, the spin gets entangled with the momentum in Lorentz-boosted reference frames, and on the other hand, for a particle moving in a superposition of velocities, it is impossible to “jump” to its rest frame, where spin is unambiguously defined. Here, we find a quantum reference frame transformation corresponding to a ‘superposition of Lorentz boosts,’ allowing us to transform to the rest frame of a particle that is in a superposition of relativistic momenta with respect to the laboratory frame. This enables us to first move to the particle’s rest frame, define there the spin measurements (via the Stern-Gerlach experimental procedure), and then move back to the laboratory frame. In this way, we find a set of ‘relativistic Stern-Gerlach measurements’ in the laboratory frame, and a set of observables satisfying the spin $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra. This operational procedure offers a concrete way of testing the relativistic features of the spin, and opens to the possibility of devising quantum information protocols for spin in the special-relativistic regime.

I. INTRODUCTION

The description of physical systems is standardly given in terms of coordinates as defined by reference frames. Thanks to the principle of covariance, stating the equivalence of all descriptions regardless of the choice of the reference frame, it is possible to choose the reference frame where the relevant dynamical quantities can be most conveniently described. For example, it is typically easier to describe the dynamics of a system from the point of view of its rest frame, because only internal degrees of freedom contribute to the dynamics in the rest frame.

However, when the external degrees of freedom (momentum) of the system are in a quantum superposition from the perspective of the laboratory, no classical reference frame transformation can map the description of physics from the laboratory to the rest frame. However, this can be achieved via a quantum reference frame (QRF) transformation between two frames moving in a superposition of velocities relative to one another. In order to achieve such change of quantum reference frame in the nonrelativistic regime, a formalism was introduced in Ref. [1] to change the description to a reference frame which is in a quantum relationship with the initial one. This QRF transformation only depends on relational quantities, [1–3]. An immediate consequence of the formalism is that entanglement and superposition are QRF-dependent features. This formalism naturally leads to the possibility of identifying the rest frame of a quantum system in an operational way.

Here, we further develop this approach in the case of a relativistic quantum particle with spin, with the goal of finding an operational description of the spin in a special-relativistic setting. Spin is operationally defined in the rest frame of a particle (or, to a good approximation, for slow velocities) via the Stern-Gerlach experiment. When the particle has relativistic velocities, the spin degree of freedom transforms in a momentum-dependent way. If a Stern-Gerlach measurement is performed on a particle in a pure quantum state moving in a superposition of relativistic velocities, the operational identification of the spin fails, because no orientation of the Stern-Gerlach apparatus returns an outcome with unit probability. This happens because, as shown in Ref. [4], the reduced density matrix of the spin degree of freedom is mixed when a Lorentz boost is performed and the momentum is traced

FIG. 1: (a) The state of a Dirac particle A with spin \tilde{A} as seen from the laboratory perspective (C). When the state is in a superposition of relativistic velocities $-v_1$ and $-v_2$, the spin degree of freedom and the momentum degree of freedom are no longer separable. (b) The state of the spin \tilde{A} and of the laboratory C as seen in the rest frame of the quantum particle A. In this quantum reference frame, the spin is operationally defined by means of the Stern-Gerlach experiment.

out. The question arises whether it is possible to find ‘covariant measurements’ of the spin and possibly momentum, which predict invariant probabilities in different Lorentzian reference frames also for the case of a quantum relativistic particle moving in a superposition of velocities. In this case, it would be possible to map the unambiguous description of spin in the rest frame of the particle to the frame of the laboratory, and therefore derive the corresponding observables to be measured in the laboratory frame to verify spin with probability one.

The question about finding such covariant measurements is motivated by the ubiquitous applications where the spin degree of freedom is used as a qubit, to encode and transmit quantum information. Such protocols are no longer valid in a relativistic context, thus limiting the range of applicability of techniques involving spin as a quantum information carrier. It is then important to explore possible alternative methods which could overcome this limitation. In the context of relativistic quantum information, this question has been extensively discussed [4–15] in relation to Wigner rotations [16–18] and has been related to the problem of identifying a covariant spin operator, which has arisen in the early times of quantum mechanics [19–21]. Since then, a multitude of relativistic spin operators have been proposed [22], such as the Frenkel [20], the Pauli-Lubański [23–25], the Pryce [26], the Foldy-Wouthuysen [27, 28], the Czachor [29] the Fleming [30] the Chakrabarti [31], and the Fradkin-Good [32] spin operators.

Here, we introduce ‘superposition of Lorentz boosts’ which allow us to “jump” into the rest frame of a relativistic quantum particle even if the particle is *not* in a momentum eigenstate. In the rest frame, the spin observables fulfill the spin $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra (the algebra of a qubit) and are operationally defined through the Stern-Gerlach experiment. We transform the set of spin observables in the rest frame back to an isomorphic set of observables in the laboratory frame. The transformed observables are in general entangled in the spin and momentum degrees of freedom. The set fulfills the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra and is operationally defined through a ‘relativistic Stern-Gerlach experiment’: we construct the interaction and the measurement between the spin-momentum degrees of freedom and the electromagnetic field in the laboratory frame which gives the same probabilities as the Stern-Gerlach experiment in the rest frame. This set of observables in the laboratory frame allows us to partition the total Hilbert space into two (highly degenerate) subspaces corresponding to the two outcomes “spin up” and “spin down”. Hence, with QRFs techniques the relativistic spin can effectively be described as a qubit in an operationally well-defined way.

II. A RELATIVISTIC STERN-GERLACH EXPERIMENT

In the following, we build a QRF transformation between the reference frame of a laboratory C of mass m_C and the rest frame of the external degrees of freedom A of a relativistic quantum particle of mass $m_A > 0$ with spin degrees of freedom \tilde{A} , as illustrated in Fig. 1. We do not assume that

the particle A has a sharp momentum from the point of view of the reference frame C, but allow it to have any quantum state. This implies that there is a non-classical relationship between the initial and the final reference frame, i.e., that the rest frame A and the laboratory frame C are not related by a standard boost transformation. We show in this section how to generalise the boost transformation to this case. Formally, the situation we consider can be described by taking the one-particle sector of the positive-energy solutions of the Dirac equation¹ in the Foldy-Wouthuysen representation [27].

Following Ref. [1], when we “stand” in the rest frame of a particle, we describe all the systems external to the particle, but not the external degrees of freedom (i.e., the momentum degrees of freedom) of the particle itself. Hence, the quantum state describes the relational information in a given reference frame. In the reference frame in which A is at rest, the quantum state describes the internal degrees of freedom \tilde{A} and the laboratory C. For simplicity, we consider that the particle and the laboratory are moving with constant velocity relative to each other and define the x axis along the direction of the relative motion. The total state of the spin and the laboratory is assumed to be

$$|\Psi\rangle_{\tilde{A}C}^{(A)} = |\vec{\sigma}\rangle_{\tilde{A}} |\psi\rangle_C, \quad (1)$$

where $|\vec{\sigma}\rangle_{\tilde{A}}$ is any vector representing the state of the spin in the rest frame A, and can be tomographically verified by performing a Stern-Gerlach measurement. The state of the laboratory has a momentum-basis representation along the x direction (at this stage, we neglect the quantum state in the y and z direction) $|\psi\rangle_C = \int d\mu_C(\pi_C) \psi(\pi_C) |\pi_C\rangle_C$, where $d\mu_C(\pi_C) = \frac{d\pi_C}{(2\pi)^{1/2} \sqrt{2(m_C^2 c^2 + \pi_C^2)}}$ is the Lorentz-covariant integration measure.

We now construct the transformation corresponding to the “superposition of Lorentz boosts” to the QRF of the laboratory. The unitary operator to boost to the QRF C is

$$\hat{S}_L = \mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)} U_{\tilde{A}}(\hat{\pi}_C), \quad (2)$$

where $U_{\tilde{A}}(\hat{\pi}_C)$ is a unitary transformation acting on the total Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{\tilde{A}} \otimes \mathcal{H}_C$ (notice that $\hat{\pi}_C$ is an operator), and $\mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)}$ is the ‘generalised parity operator’ introduced in Ref. [1], whose explicit expression is $\mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)} = P_{AC} \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \log \sqrt{\frac{m_A}{m_C}} (\hat{q}_C \hat{\pi}_C + \hat{\pi}_C \hat{q}_C)\right)$, where P_{AC} is the parity-swap operator mapping $\hat{x}_A \rightarrow -\hat{q}_C$ and $\hat{p}_A \rightarrow -\hat{\pi}_C$ (and viceversa), where \hat{q}_C , $\hat{\pi}_C$ are canonically-conjugated one-particle operators of C in the reference frame of A and \hat{x}_A , \hat{p}_A are canonically-conjugated one-particle operators of A in the reference frame of C. Additionally to the action of P_{AC} , the operator $\mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)}$ rescales the momentum of A by the ratio of the masses of A and C, i.e., $\mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)} \hat{p}_A \mathcal{P}_{CA}^{(v)\dagger} = -\frac{m_A}{m_C} \hat{\pi}_C$. This enforces the physical condition that the velocity of A is mapped to the opposite of the velocity of C via the transformation². The operator \hat{S}_L can be defined via its action on a basis of the total Hilbert space of the spin and the laboratory $\hat{S}_L |\vec{\sigma}\rangle_{\tilde{A}} |\pi\rangle_C = |-\frac{m_A}{m_C} \pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}$, where the state $|p; \Sigma_p\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}$ is defined via a standard Lorentz boost $\hat{U}(L_p)$ from the rest frame as $|p; \Sigma_p\rangle_{A\tilde{A}} = \hat{U}(L_p) |k; \vec{\sigma}\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}$ and $k = (mc, \vec{0})$ is the momentum in the rest frame. The state $|p; \Sigma_p\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}$ is an eigenvector of the Pauli-Lubański operator $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu = (L_{-p})^\mu_\nu \hat{\sigma}^\nu$, where $\hat{\sigma}^\nu = (0, \hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{\sigma}_z)$ are the Pauli operators (see Appendix A). In Appendix B we derive the transformation \hat{S}_L in terms of standard Lorentz boosts connecting two relativistic reference frames where the parameter of the boost transformation is promoted to an operator.

Notice that here we use “superposition of Lorentz boosts” because we describe physics from the point of view of two QRFs moving in a superposition of relativistic velocities relative to each other. This is different to the definition of such transformations given in Ref. [1], where the transformation

¹ For simplicity, we only consider spin-1/2 particles, but the method can be straightforwardly applied to arbitrary spin.

² For a relativistic particle the relation between the i -th velocity component and the momentum is $v_i = \frac{p_i}{m_i} \left(1 + \frac{|\vec{p}|^2}{m_i^2 c^2}\right)^{-1/2}$, where $|\vec{p}|^2$ is the norm of the spatial momentum. Therefore, only the ratio between momentum and mass determines the velocity.

is written as the classical reference frame transformation with the parameter of the transformation promoted to an operator, because the transformation of the spin degree of freedom alone does not correspond to a Lorentz boost. Notice, however, that the QRF transformation would be completely analogous to those in Ref. [1] if we considered a Klein-Gordon field instead of the spin \hat{A} . In this case, the QRF transformation would be given by a Lorentz boost, with the parameter v replaced by a function of the operator $\hat{\pi}_C$, followed by a generalised parity-swap operator.

The state of A and \hat{A} expressed in the laboratory frame is $|\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}}^{(C)} = \hat{S}_L |\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}}^{(A)}$, and is explicitly written as

$$|\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}}^{(C)} = \left(\frac{m_C}{m_A}\right)^2 \int d\mu_A(p_A) \psi\left(-\frac{m_C}{m_A}p_A\right) |p_A; \Sigma_{p_A}\rangle_{A\hat{A}}, \quad (3)$$

where $d\mu_A(p_A) = \frac{dp_A}{(2\pi)^{1/2} \sqrt{2(m_A^2 c^2 + p_A^2)}}$ and the spin degree of freedom cannot be separated anymore from the momentum degree of freedom, which means that the state is not a product state in the laboratory frame. Notice that the effect of the \hat{S}_L transformation is to apply the usual boost transformation conditional on C 's momentum degree of freedom. In the laboratory frame C , unless particle A is in a sharp momentum state, no spin measurement in a standard Stern-Gerlach experiment would give a result with probability one, because of two reasons: the spin and momentum are no longer separable, and the relation between the laboratory and the rest frame is not a standard (classical) reference frame transformation. Our goal is to devise a different measurement in the laboratory reference frame, possibly involving both the spin and momentum degrees of freedom, which gives the same probability distribution as a standard Stern-Gerlach would give, if performed in the rest frame.

In order to devise such measurement we note that, in the laboratory frame, it is possible to define the observables corresponding to the spin operators in the rest frame by transforming the spin, as defined in the rest frame, with a QRF transformation

$$\hat{\Xi}_i = \hat{S}_L (\hat{\sigma}_i \otimes \mathbb{1}_C) \hat{S}_L^\dagger, \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (4)$$

In terms of the momenta and of the manifestly covariant Pauli-Lubański operator $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu$, $\mu = 0, \dots, 3$, the operators $\hat{\Xi}$ are expressed as (see Appendix C for more details) $\hat{\Xi} = \vec{\Sigma}_p - \frac{\gamma_A}{\gamma_A + 1} (\vec{\Sigma}_p \cdot \vec{\beta}_A) \vec{\beta}_A$, where $\gamma_A = \sqrt{1 + \frac{p_A^2}{m_A^2 c^2}}$ and $\vec{\beta}_A = \frac{\vec{p}_A}{\sqrt{m_A^2 c^2 + p_A^2}}$. By definition, these operators satisfy the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra $[\hat{\Xi}_i, \hat{\Xi}_j] = i\epsilon_{ijk} \hat{\Xi}_k$, and have the same eigenvalues as the Pauli operators $\hat{\sigma}_i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$. This last property can be easily checked by choosing an eigenvector $|i_\pm\rangle$ of the operator $\hat{\sigma}_i$ in the rest frame A , such that $\hat{\sigma}_i |\lambda_i\rangle = \lambda_i |\lambda_i\rangle$ and by noting that $\hat{\Xi}_i \hat{S}_L |\lambda_i\rangle_{\hat{A}} |\psi\rangle_C = \lambda_i \hat{S}_L |\lambda_i\rangle_{\hat{A}} |\psi\rangle_C$. Hence, it is possible to partition the total Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_{\hat{A}}$ into two equivalence classes, defined as

$$\mathcal{H}_0 = \left\{ |\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_{\hat{A}} \text{ s.t. } |\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}} \sim \hat{S}_L |0\rangle_{\hat{A}} |\psi\rangle_C, \forall |\psi\rangle_C \in \mathcal{H}_C \right\}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_1 = \left\{ |\Phi\rangle_{A\hat{A}} \in \mathcal{H}_A \otimes \mathcal{H}_{\hat{A}} \text{ s.t. } |\Phi\rangle_{A\hat{A}} \sim \hat{S}_L |1\rangle_{\hat{A}} |\phi\rangle_C, \forall |\phi\rangle_C \in \mathcal{H}_C \right\}, \quad (5b)$$

where $|0\rangle_{\hat{A}}$ and $|1\rangle_{\hat{A}}$ are the eigenvectors of $\hat{\sigma}_3$ ³ and two states are said to be equivalent, i.e., $|\Psi\rangle_{A\hat{A}} \sim \hat{S}_L |i\rangle_{\hat{A}} |\psi\rangle_C$, if they are both eigenvectors of the $\hat{\Xi}_3$ operator with the same eigenvalue. We can then build a partition of the Hilbert space into two highly degenerate subspaces, one corresponding to the “spin up” and other to the “spin down” eigenvalue, and on which it is possible to define a set of

³ Notice that we could have chosen any other Pauli operator to define this partition.

FIG. 2: The relativistic Stern-Gerlach experiment as seen from the QRF A (above) and from the QRF C (below). In the rest frame of particle A, the spin is operationally defined via the Stern-Gerlach experiment. To measure spin along direction \vec{n} the spin (Pauli operator) $\vec{\sigma}$ is coupled to an inhomogeneous magnetic field oriented along \vec{n} . The particle is then deflected towards the direction \vec{n} and $-\vec{n}$ corresponding to outcome “spin up” and “spin down” respectively. When transforming to the laboratory frame C, the magnetic field and the spin transform with a superposition of Lorentz boosts for v_1 and v_2 . The interaction Hamiltonian is also transformed, giving rise to a coupling between the transformed vector $\vec{S}_\Lambda(\vec{B}^{(A)}) = \gamma_A \left[\vec{B}^{(C)} - \frac{\gamma_A}{\gamma_A+1} (\vec{\beta}_A \cdot \vec{B}^{(C)}) \vec{\beta}_A + (\vec{\beta}_A \times \vec{E}^{(C)}) \right]$ aligned in the same direction \vec{n} as the magnetic field in the rest frame, and the transformed spin operator $\vec{\Xi}$. The particle is again deflected either to \vec{n} or $-\vec{n}$ corresponding to the outcome “spin up” and “spin down” respectively. The probability of detecting the outcomes “spin up” and “spin down” is preserved under change of QRF.

operators satisfying the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra, which can be used to encode or decode information of a single qubit.

The operators $\vec{\Xi}$ in general act on both the external and the internal degrees of freedom of the particle. Operationally, they can be defined via a “relativistic Stern-Gerlach experiment,” illustrated in Fig. 2. Traditionally, in a Stern-Gerlach experiment, the spin measurement is performed by applying a magnetic field, which interacts with the spin as $\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\sigma}$ and is inhomogeneous along the direction of its orientation, i.e., $\vec{B} = B(\vec{r} \cdot \vec{n})\vec{n}$, where \vec{n} gives the direction and $\vec{r} = (x, y, z)$. If the magnetic field is aligned precisely in the direction in which the spin state is prepared, the outcome is obtained with certainty. However, if the particle carrying the spin is moving in a superposition of relativistic velocities, no measurement of the spin alone in the laboratory frame will return the result with probability one in general. To treat such a case we set up a hypothetical Stern-Gerlach experiment in the rest frame of the particle, where the interaction Hamiltonian is $H_{int}^{(A)} = \mu \vec{B}^{(A)} \cdot \vec{\sigma}$ and μ is a coupling constant. We assume that the direction in which the magnetic field is aligned \vec{n} is orthogonal to the direction of the boost x . Formally, this geometric configuration requires to enlarge the Hilbert space of the laboratory to the z direction, and modify our previous definition of the state in Eq. (1) as $|\psi\rangle_C = |\psi_x\rangle_C |\psi_z\rangle_C$, where $|\psi_x\rangle_C$ transforms with \hat{S}_L and $|\psi_z\rangle_C$ is left invariant by the transformation \hat{S}_L , except for the fact that the label is changed from C to A, i.e., $\hat{S}_L |\psi_z\rangle_C = |\psi_z\rangle_A$. Additionally, we assume that the motion in the z direction is non relativistic. We then transform the Hamiltonian to the laboratory frame via the QRF transformation \hat{S}_L . Knowing that the magnetic field transforms under superposition of Lorentz boosts as $\vec{S}_\Lambda(\vec{B}^{(A)}) = \gamma_A \left[\vec{B}^{(C)} - \frac{\gamma_A}{\gamma_A+1} (\vec{\beta}_A \cdot \vec{B}^{(C)}) \vec{\beta}_A + (\vec{\beta}_A \times \vec{E}^{(C)}) \right]$, we find that the interaction Hamiltonian $H_{int}^{(A)}$ is transformed to

$$H_{int}^{(C)} = \mu \gamma_A^{-1} \vec{S}_\Lambda(\vec{B}^{(A)}) \cdot \vec{\Xi}. \quad (6)$$

It is straightforward to check that the direction of $\vec{S}_\Lambda(\vec{B}^{(A)})$ is also \vec{n} , therefore the deflection of the particle in the laboratory frame happens in the same direction as in the rest frame. Notice that,

since both the quantum state and the observables transform unitarily, probabilities are automatically conserved after the change of QRF. In particular, if in the rest frame of the particle A the Stern Gerlach measurement detects that the spin is “up” with probability one, the “relativistic Stern-Gerlach” experiment in the laboratory frame with the interaction Hamiltonian of Eq. (6) will also detect “spin up” with probability one.

It is worth noting that the interaction Hamiltonian of Eq. (6) is covariant, because the quantity $H^0 := \gamma_A H_{int}^{(C)}$ transforms like the zero-component of a 4-vector. Therefore, the Schrödinger equation in the reference frame of A, $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt_A} |\psi\rangle_{AC}^{(A)} = H_{int}^{(A)} |\psi\rangle_{AC}^{(A)}$, where t_A is the proper time in the rest frame of A, is mapped to $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt_C} |\psi\rangle_{AA}^{(C)} = H_{int}^{(C)} |\psi\rangle_{AA}^{(C)}$, where t_C is the proper time in the rest frame of C and the relation $t_C = \gamma_A t_A$ holds. The general, manifestly covariant expression of H^0 is

$$H^0 = \frac{1}{2} \eta^{0\rho} \epsilon_{\rho\mu\nu\lambda} \hat{\Sigma}_{pA}^\mu F^{\nu\lambda}, \quad (7)$$

where $\eta^{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$ is the Minkowski metric, $F^{\nu\lambda}$ is the electromagnetic tensor and $\epsilon_{\rho\mu\nu\lambda}$ is the totally antisymmetric tensor such that $\epsilon_{0123} = 1$.

In order to complete the measurement, we now have to project along the z direction. In order to distinguish the state of the spin, it is enough to know whether the particle is deflected upwards ($z_C > 0$) or downwards ($z_C < 0$). Formally, this projection is represented via the two operators $\hat{\Pi}_+^{(A)} = \int_0^{+\infty} dz_c |z_C\rangle_C \langle z_C|$ and $\hat{\Pi}_-^{(A)} = \int_{-\infty}^0 dz_c |z_C\rangle_C \langle z_C|$ and can represent the half-planes of a screen at which the particle is detected. Since the z direction is invariant under boosts along x , the measurement in the laboratory frame C is identical to the measurement in QRF A, i.e., $\hat{\Pi}_\pm^{(C)} = \hat{\Pi}_\pm^{(A)}$. Note that the particle arrives at the screen in a superposition of times in the measurement in the laboratory frame C, as compared to the one in the rest frame A, because of the relation between the proper times $t_C = \gamma_A t_A$ and the fact that the particle moves in a superposition of velocities. Therefore, measuring the time of arrival of the particle would provide information about the momentum of the particle.

The QRF transformation provides the description of the same experiment from the point of view of two different QRFs, which move in a superposition of velocities relative to each other. This treatment of the relativistic Stern-Gerlach experiment makes it possible to associate an operational meaning to the spin of a relativistic quantum particle, thus solving the problem of encoding quantum information in a particle with spin degrees of freedom as in a qubit.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have provided an operational description of the spin of a special-relativistic quantum particle. Such operational description is hard to obtain with standard methods due to the combined effect of special relativity, which makes the spin and momentum not separable, and quantum mechanics, which makes it impossible to jump to the rest frame with a standard reference frame transformation. We have introduced the ‘superposition of Lorentz boosts’ transformation to the rest frame of a quantum particle, moving in a superposition of relativistic velocities from the point of view of the laboratory. We have found how the state transforms under such quantum reference frame transformation and identified a set of observables in the laboratory frame which satisfies the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra and has the same eigenvalues as the spin in its rest frame. In addition, this set complies with the desiderata for a relativistic spin operator in Ref. [22]: it commutes with the free Dirac Hamiltonian, it satisfies the $\mathfrak{su}(2)$ algebra, and it has the same eigenvalues as the spin in its rest frame. In addition, it has the correct nonrelativistic limit. It can be easily shown, in fact, that our operator $\vec{\Xi}$ coincides with the Foldy-Wouthuysen spin operator [27, 28]. Thanks to the unitarity of the transformation, probabilities are the same in the rest frame and in the laboratory frame. Finally, we have generalised the Stern-Gerlach to the special-relativistic regime by means of a transformation of the interaction

Hamiltonian from the rest frame to the laboratory frame. Such generalisation opens to the possibility of performing quantum information protocols with spin in the special-relativistic regime.

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Appendix A: Lorentz transformations of the spin

The spin of a particle has a natural definition in the rest frame. In a different reference frame, quantum field theory predicts that a more general quantity, the total angular momentum, is conserved, and spin alone is no longer operationally well defined, because the splitting of the angular momentum and spin momentum is not unique. However, it is possible to associate a 4-vector to the spin operator, which can then be transformed in a covariant way. The treatment can be found, e.g. in Ref. [33]. In the rest frame, the components of the covariant spin are $\hat{\sigma}^\nu = (\hat{0}, \hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{\sigma}_z)$, where $\hat{\sigma}_i$, $i = x, y, z$, are the Pauli operators, which generate the group $SU(2)$. We now want to boost the state to a reference frame in which the particle moves with momentum $\vec{p} = m\gamma\vec{v}$, where m is the mass of the particle, $\gamma = \sqrt{1 + \frac{\vec{p}^2}{m^2c^2}} = \left(1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)^{-1/2}$ and \vec{v} is the velocity of the particle in the new reference frame. We define by $U(L_{-p})$ the operator representing a pure Lorentz boost to the new reference frame, where the boost operator L_p is explicitly written as the matrix

$$L_p = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \frac{p_0}{mc} & -\frac{p_i}{mc} \\ \hline -\frac{p_i}{mc} & \delta_{ij} + \frac{p_i p_j}{mc(p_0 + mc)} \end{array} \right), \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, 3$. The spin operator transforms as $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu = (L_{-p})^\mu_\nu \hat{\sigma}^\nu$, where

$$\hat{\Sigma}_p^0 = \gamma \vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{\sigma}; \quad \vec{\Sigma}_p = \vec{\sigma} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} (\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{\sigma}) \vec{\beta}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{v}}{c} = \frac{\vec{p}}{\sqrt{m^2c^2 + |\vec{p}|^2}}$. Notice that the introduction of the fourth spin component does not add degrees of freedom, because the 4-vector has to satisfy the covariant constraint $\eta_{\mu\nu} p^\mu \Sigma_p^\nu = 0$, where $\eta_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$ is the Minkowski metric. The eigenstates $|p, \Sigma_p\rangle$ of the $\hat{\Sigma}_p$ operator live in a Hilbert space which is not separable in the internal degrees of freedom (spin) and the external ones (momentum). Formally, the total Hilbert space can be described as a fiber bundle, the base manifold being the space of square-integrable functions and the fibers being the two-dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_p , representing the spin degree of freedom. The operator $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu$ coincides, up to a factor m_A , with the Pauli-Lubański relativistic spin operator.

Appendix B: Derivation of the quantum reference frame transformation

The QRF transformation \hat{S}_L can be derived by considering a tripartite Hilbert space of the external degrees of freedom of the particle (A), the spin of the particle (\tilde{A}), and the laboratory (C). A general basis element, in the rest frame of the particle A is $|k_A; \vec{\sigma}\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C$, where $k_A^\mu = (m_A c, \vec{0})$. If we wish to change to the QRF of the laboratory C, we need to apply a standard Lorentz boost to the state of the particle $A\tilde{A}$, where the boost parameter is controlled by the momentum of the laboratory $\hat{\pi}_C$, and then boost the laboratory state by the momentum of A. The full transformation reads

$$\hat{S}_{ext} = \hat{U}_C^\dagger(L_{\frac{m_C}{m_A}\hat{p}_A})\hat{U}_{A\tilde{A}}(L_{-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\hat{\pi}_C}), \quad (\text{B1})$$

where $\hat{U}_X(L_{\hat{p}_Y})$ (with $X \neq Y$) is the standard Lorentz boost by the momentum operator \hat{p}_Y (i.e., the standard Lorentz boost where the parameter p has been promoted to the operator \hat{p}_Y), acting on the Hilbert spaces X and Y as $\hat{U}_{A\tilde{A}}(L_{-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\hat{\pi}_C})|k_A; \vec{\sigma}\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C = |-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C$ and $\hat{U}_C^\dagger(L_{\frac{m_C}{m_A}\hat{p}_A})|-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C = |-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|k_C\rangle_C$. The action on a basis of the total Hilbert space is

$$\hat{S}_{ext}|k_A; \vec{\sigma}\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C = |-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}|k_C\rangle_C, \quad (\text{B2})$$

with $k_C^\mu = (m_C c, \vec{0})$. We notice that the Hilbert spaces of the QRF, A and C respectively before and after the transformation, are irrelevant and can be omitted, as they are only labelled by the zero momentum 4-vector k_A and k_C and represent no dynamical degrees of freedom (their quantum states do not change in time). Therefore, in accordance with the QRF formalism introduced in Ref. [1], we can drop them and write the QRF transformation in the more compact form \hat{S}_L in Eq. (2) in the main text

$$\hat{S}_L|\vec{\sigma}\rangle_{\tilde{A}}|\pi\rangle_C = |-\frac{m_A}{m_C}\pi; \Sigma_\pi\rangle_{A\tilde{A}}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

This transformation can be explicitly written as

$$\hat{S}_L = \mathcal{P}_{AC}^{(v)}\hat{U}_{\tilde{A}}(\hat{\pi}_C), \quad (\text{B4})$$

where $\hat{U}_{\tilde{A}}(\hat{\pi}_C)$ is a unitary operator acting on the joint Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}_{\tilde{A}} \otimes \mathcal{H}_C$, and $\mathcal{P}_{AC}^{(v)} = P_{AC} \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} \log \sqrt{\frac{m_A}{m_C}} (\hat{q}_C \hat{\pi}_C + \hat{\pi}_C \hat{q}_C)\right)$ is the ‘generalised parity-swap operator’ introduced in Ref. [1]. Here, P_{AC} is the parity-swap operator mapping $\hat{x}_A \rightarrow -\hat{q}_C$ and $\hat{p}_A \rightarrow -\hat{\pi}_C$ (and viceversa). Additionally to the action of P_{AC} , the operator $\mathcal{P}_{AC}^{(v)}$ rescales the momentum of A by the ratio of the masses of A and C, i.e., $\mathcal{P}_{AC}^{(v)}\hat{p}_A\mathcal{P}_{AC}^{(v)\dagger} = -\frac{m_A}{m_C}\hat{\pi}_C$.

Appendix C: Action of the spin operator

Here, we give an explicit derivation of how the operators $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu$ and $\vec{\Xi}$ act on a basis of the Hilbert space. We describe the state and the operators from the point of view of the laboratory frame C, and we drop the subscripts A and \tilde{A} . Here, $\hat{U}(L_p)$ is the standard Lorentz boost to the frame where the particle has momentum p . By definition, $\hat{U}(L_p)|k, \vec{\sigma}\rangle = |p, \Sigma_p\rangle$, where $|k, \vec{\sigma}\rangle = \sum_\lambda c_\lambda |k, \lambda\rangle$

represented in some spin basis. We can now write the action of the Pauli-Lubański operator as

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu |p, \Sigma_p\rangle &= \hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu \hat{U}(L_p) |k, \vec{\sigma}\rangle = \hat{U}(L_p) \hat{U}^\dagger(L_p) \hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu \hat{U}(L_p) |k, \vec{\sigma}\rangle = \\
&= \hat{U}(L_p) (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu \hat{\Sigma}_p^\nu |k, \vec{\sigma}\rangle = \sum_\lambda c_\lambda \hat{U}(L_p) (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu \hat{\sigma}^\nu |k, \lambda\rangle = \\
&= \sum_{\lambda, \lambda'} c_\lambda \hat{U}(L_p) (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu [\sigma^\nu]_{\lambda' \lambda} |k, \lambda'\rangle = \sum_{\lambda, \lambda'} c_\lambda (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu [\sigma^\nu]_{\lambda' \lambda} |p, \Sigma_p(\lambda')\rangle = \\
&= (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu \hat{\sigma}^\nu |p, \Sigma_p\rangle,
\end{aligned} \tag{C1}$$

where we have used the fact that the Pauli-Lubański operator reduces to the Pauli operators $\hat{\sigma}^\nu = (\hat{0}, \hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y, \hat{\sigma}_z)$ in the rest frame and L_p has been defined in Eq. (A1). From this result, it is easy to see that the operator $\hat{\Sigma}_p$ is obtained by boosting the 4-vector $\hat{\sigma}^\nu$ from the rest frame as $\hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu = (L_{-p})_\nu^\mu \hat{\sigma}^\nu$. With an analogous method it is possible to show that $\hat{\Xi}^i |p, \Sigma_p\rangle = \hat{U}(L_p) (\mathbb{1} \otimes \vec{\sigma}) \hat{U}^\dagger(L_p) |p, \Sigma_p\rangle = (L_p)_\mu^i \hat{\Sigma}_p^\mu |p, \Sigma_p\rangle$. Thus, the action of the two operators $\hat{\Sigma}_p$ and $\hat{\Xi}$ is obtained by Lorentz-transforming the other.

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